
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 2

Computing emission measures with the INTEGRAL_CALC
routine

Version 1.2, 12-Jul-2023, Peter Young

1 Overview

An emission line intensity can be converted into an emission measure value using the CHIANTI routine INTEGRAL_CALC. This report explains how the routine works.

2 Uses

The intensity of an emission line reflects the amount of emitting plasma but it is necessary to account for atomic physics parameters and the element abundance to yield this estimate. The amount of emitting plasma is usually expressed as the *column emission measure* which is $\sim N_e^2 h$ where h is the depth of the emitting column and N_e is the electron number density. In the case of the solar atmosphere a line intensity represents an integral of the emission from large spatial regions that likely have a range of densities and temperatures and so determining the plasma distribution usually involves solving complex integral equations for multiple emission lines to yield a differential emission measure curve.

Pottasch (1964) came up with a simple method that allows a single line intensity to be directly converted into an emission measure value, and the method described here is a modification of this work. An example of the application of the method is given in Tripathi et al. (2010) where emission measures are derived from multiple emission lines observed by the Hinode/EIS instrument.

3 Method

For historical reasons INTEGRAL_CALC uses different notation for the emission line intensity than that used in the CHIANTI User Guide (CUG), so the two are reconciled here.

Equation 11 of the CUG gives the following expression for the intensity, I , of an optically thin emission line

$$I(\lambda_{ij}) = \int Ab(X)G(T, \lambda_{ij}, N_e)N_eN_H dh \quad (1)$$

where λ_{ij} is the wavelength corresponding to atomic transition $i-j$, $Ab(X)$ is the abundance of element X relative to hydrogen, G is the contribution function (note that C is used in the CUG), N_e and N_H are the electron number densities of electrons and hydrogen, and h is the column depth of the plasma. G is given by

$$G(T, \lambda_{ij}, N_e) = \frac{h\nu_{ij}}{4\pi} \frac{A_{ij}}{N_e} \frac{N_j(X^{+m})}{N(X^{+m})} \frac{N(X^{+m})}{N(X)}. \quad (2)$$

where $h\nu_{ij} = \Delta E$ is the energy for the transition, A_{ij} is the radiative decay rate, $N_j(X^{+m})$ is the population of the emitting level j of the ion X^{+m} . We can re-write this as

$$G_\lambda(T, N_e) = \frac{\Delta E}{4\pi} \frac{n_j A_{ij}}{N_e} F(T) \quad (3)$$

where n_j is the population of level relative to the population of the emitting ion as a whole and $F_m(T)$ is the ionization fraction of ion X^{+m} .

We define an alternative version of the contribution function as

$$\mathcal{G}_\lambda(T, N_e) = \frac{4\pi}{\Delta E} \frac{N_H}{N_e} G_\lambda(T, N_e) \quad (4)$$

(note that N_H/N_e is approximately a constant with value around 0.85 for solar plasmas with temperatures $\geq 10^5$ K) and so Eq. 1 becomes

$$4\pi I_\lambda = \Delta E A b(X) \int \mathcal{G}_\lambda(T, N_e) N_e^2 dh. \quad (5)$$

Fundamental approximations behind INTEGRAL_CALC are to assume the density is a known constant in the region the line is formed, and that \mathcal{G} is constant in the temperature region where \mathcal{G} has its peak value, and zero outside of this region. Formally, we define

$$\mathcal{G}_\lambda^*(T) = \begin{cases} C_\lambda & |\log T - \log T_{\text{mem}}| < 0.15 \\ 0 & |\log T - \log T_{\text{mem}}| > 0.15 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

for some constant C_λ , where T_{mem} is the temperature at which \mathcal{G} has its maximum value. We require that

$$\int \mathcal{G}_\lambda(T) dT = \int \mathcal{G}_\lambda^*(T) dT \quad (7)$$

and so C_λ is given by

$$C_\lambda = \frac{\int \mathcal{G}_\lambda(T) dT}{T_{\text{mem}}(10^{0.15} - 10^{-0.15})}. \quad (8)$$

Eq. 5 is then written as

$$4\pi I_\lambda = \Delta E A b(X) C_\lambda \int N_e^2 dh \quad (9)$$

$$= \Delta E A b(X) C_\lambda \text{EM}(h) \quad (10)$$

where $\text{EM}(h)$ is the column emission measure, thus the emission measure can be directly related to the observed line intensity. If N_e is known from a density diagnostic then the column depth can be estimated from $h = \text{EM}(h)/N_e^2$.

4 Implementation

The key part of the routine is to compute the integral which is done by computing the function

$$f_i = \ln 10 \varepsilon_{ij}(T_i, N_e) F(T_i) T_i \quad (11)$$

where ε is the line emissivity computed by the CHIANTI routine EMISS_CALC, F is the ionization fraction, T_i the temperature and N_e the electron density.

The following integral is then computed:

$$\int f d(\log T) = \sum f_i d(\log T_i) \quad (12)$$

using the IDL routine INT_TABULATED, with $\log T_i$ specified at 0.01 dex intervals.

We then have

$$C_\lambda = \frac{N_e}{0.7046 T_{\text{mem}}} \frac{N_{\text{H}}}{N_e} \sum f_i d(\log T_i) \quad (13)$$

where T_{mem} is the temperature at which the function $\varepsilon F(T)$ has its peak. The proton-to-electron ratio is computed using the IDL routine `PROTON_DENS`, which makes use of the default `CHIANTI` element abundance file (given by system variable `!abund_file`). An alternative file can be specified with the optional input `abund_file` to `INTEGRAL_CALC`.

5 Outputs

The routine gives the following outputs: T_{mem} , C_λ , $\Delta E C_\lambda$ and $4\pi/(\Delta E C_\lambda)$ which are printed to the screen. Alternatively they can be returned to IDL through the optional output `OUTSTR=`. Examples of the output from `INTEGRAL_CALC` are given in Appendix B.

6 Types of call

The most simple call is, e.g.,

```
IDL> integral_calc, 'fe_13'
```

which will display results for the 10 strongest lines. Note that user input is required to blend lines (if necessary) or plot the emissivity functions.

Results for a specific wavelength range can be printed with:

```
IDL> integral_calc, 'fe_13', wrange=[200,205]
IDL> integral_calc, 'fe_13', wrange=[200,205], /all
```

The first call will take the five strongest lines in the specified wavelength range, while the second prints all lines in the wavelength range. An example of the output from the routine is given in Appendix B.

If `INTEGRAL_CALC` is to be called from within another routine then it is necessary to directly specify a specific transition. This can be done with:

```
IDL> integral_calc, 'fe_13', index=39127, outstr=outstr
```

The index is the index of the transition within the emissivity structure produced by `EMISS_CALC`. In the example above the strong $\lambda 202.04$ line is selected.

7 The /QUICK keyword

The ionization fractions are tabulated at 0.05 dex intervals in $\log T$, and `INTEGRAL_CALC` computes the emissivities, ε , at 0.1 dex intervals as they are more slowly varying in temperature. Both quantities are interpolated onto 0.01 dex intervals for the integration.

The call to `EMISS_CALC` can be very slow for large ion models such as the coronal iron ions. For this reason a keyword `/QUICK` is available that speeds up the calculation by:

1. Only using temperatures for which the ionization fraction is $\geq F_{\max}/1000$, where F_{\max} is the maximum of the ionization fraction.
2. Only computing the emissivities for a reduced number of temperatures (the present implementation uses 6 temperatures) that span the ionization fraction temperatures.

This approximation is found to work well for the coronal iron ions, giving results within 1% of the original implementation. There are examples where `/QUICK` does not work well, for example `H I` and `O VI`, where the ionization fraction extends over a wide temperature range. The code has an in-built check on whether the approximation is working well and a warning is printed if not.

References

- Pottasch, S. R. 1964, *Space Sci. Rev.*, 3, 816, doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/BF00177958>
- Tripathi, D., Mason, H. E., Del Zanna, G., & Young, P. R. 2010, *A&A*, 518, A42, doi: <http://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/200913883>

A Document history

Version 1.2, 12-Jul-2023. Updated reference to Tripathi paper; moved document to Overleaf.

Version 1.1, 6-Feb-2017. Revised Sect. 3 to reconcile with CUG; added Appendix.

B Example output

The following output was generated using CHIANTI 8. The output parameters should be related to Eq. 10. “Emiss ind” is the index of the transition with the structure returned by the routine EMISS.CALC.

```
IDL> integral_calc,'fe_13',wrange=[200,205]
```

```
Ion balance file: /Users/young/ssw/packages/chianti/dbase/ioneq/chianti.ioneq
```

```
Log (density/cm-3): 10.0
```

	Emiss ind	Lambda	T_mem	C_lambda	DE*C_lambda	4pi/DE*C_lambda
1	26183	200.021	6.25	1.0352e-10	1.0278e-20	1.2226e+21
2	26381	201.126	6.25	1.1015e-10	1.0877e-20	1.1553e+21
3	26520	202.044	6.25	1.4385e-10	1.4140e-20	8.8869e+20
4	26842	203.795	6.25	1.3829e-10	1.3477e-20	9.3244e+20
5	26851	203.826	6.25	3.8453e-10	3.7468e-20	3.3539e+20